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“LITERARY ANALYSIS OF THE FILM HUNGER GAMES”

The Hunger Games, a scifi/fantasy genre written by the American author, Suzanne Collins, is a prolific journey centered around a strong and young female heroine, Katniss Everdeen who lives in Panem, a *post-apocalyptic* society situated in North America. This impeccable work of Collins introduces a very futuristic dystopian post-apocalyptic society controlled by an overpowering, ruthless, and brutal totalitarian government located in the Capitol of Panem. This despotic Capitol of Panem controls most of the country's wealth and maintains its hold on its twelve districts.

The major rub of the story starts when the Capitol of Panem hosts an event called the Hunger Games forcing 24 children from poor twelve districts (one boy and one girl for each district) called “tributes” to compete and fight to the death in an arena until only one tribute survives. On the day of the nerve-wracking reaping of district 12 where Katniss an oppressed citizen is residing, her young sister, Prim, is selected as the female tribute to represent their District for the Hunger Games. Everyone in District 12 is in shocked silence. To Katniss' horror, she automatically runs to Prim and takes her sister's place as tribute in a fight-to-the-death tournament alongside Peeta Mallark, the male tribute chosen. The two are then taken into custody to be trained and groomed for the highly anticipated bloodbath for the pure entertainment of the audience only since the game is nationally televised.

To please the audience's approval, the two tributes with their mentor, Haymitch, plan for a strategy which is to pretend that there is mutual understanding going on between the two of them in order to invite sponsors and supporters of their love team which they find very indispensable to survive.

Hunger Games Feminist Analysis

Christiana (2012) in her blog discussed the feminist aspects observed in the movie *The Hunger Games*. The feminist aspects noted include culture, stereotypes, equality, power, and class. She stressed out that there are no gender roles practiced in Panem mainly because of the economic or social class of the citizens. She observed that everyone works in the fields, mines, or factories where everybody regardless of the gender receives equal pay and equal status. The people in Panem are treated unethically and do not have power to fight against the class people in the Capitol but not Katniss.

Amazingly, Katniss Everdeen possesses a mixture of “feminine” and “masculine” characteristics. As is well documented by Loobeek who analyzed the feministic side of the movie, *The Hunger Games*, Katniss, aside

from being the head of the family after her father died, is exceptionally skilled with a bow and arrow while hunting. Also, she is physically courageous and brave and is very athletic, too.

This I believe is not very common for a lady to possess such bravery and strength at her very young age (16 years old). She just opened how people view girls as modest, calm, submissive, composed or any other genuine feminine stereotypes people have on women. What I like most about her is her bravery that despite coming from a poor economic background and the struggles she encounters, she can still assert domination because of her unyielding determination and overlapping feminine and masculine attributes to make a difference in her society. Indeed, she is considered by many a rare thing in pop fiction. I consider her one of the most radical female characters to appear in any Dystopian American films as she becomes the figure of an intense radical feminist at present.

One of the reasons perhaps why she is loved and admired by a lot of critics aside from the fact that she fires up anybody's imagination is her image as the face of revolution and not Peeta or any other boys in the movie. During the slaughter games, Katniss does not become an aggressor but only kills those who attack her for self-defense in order to survive. Though it is expected to be a bloodbath where the fittest survives, her compassion towards others is still present and felt. She does not boast despite her being skillful at bows and arrows and that makes her a smart hunter.

As Scott and Dargis (2012) put it, "She is different, though, not only because she is a woman but also because she is anything but a free, rootless figure of the wilderness." Like any other ordinary person, she fights for her life and family and she is willing to sacrifice for her loved ones that we seldom see for a woman to do.

Another stereotype depicted is on the ultimate symbol of power in the country Panem, the president that is a male. Currently, male presidents run most of the countries. In this movie, we are given the notion that even in the post apocalyptic world, still male presidents take the ultimate symbol of power as if a country rests on their shoulders. The question to raise that most do not or will not give answer is *whether or not women can lead a country effectively without racial prejudice*. Thus, Hunger Games displays the roles of gender equality that everybody shares equal rights and opportunities and that women are capable of such power and responsibility as deprived of them in the western world.

One thing also that makes her very peculiar from the rest is her disinterest in romantic love. She does not need someone or a partner to complete her journey that all she needs is herself and her family. I too have the same feel about love affair.

Hunger Games Marxist Criticism

The movie further shows Marxist criticism as I evaluate the economic system of the time and place. Two worlds are introduced in the movie such as the proletariat (workers) and bourgeoisie (owners). From Marxist lens, it shows that the 12 districts work for the Capitol by providing them with their majority wealth. Also, the harsh and cruel Capitol forces the twelve districts to send two tributes for the Hunger Games every year in disagreement of the people in the said districts. Like in the movie, we can see at present that there is really a division of society going on between the rich class, the middle class, and the poor working class.

The only way to achieve justice to the unfair system is through violent revolution. Thus, Katniss proved to everybody that she is the girl on fire by plotting to overthrow the Capitol by means of revolution which coincides with Marxist thinking.

As observed, those in the Capitol take so much and obtain so much from the poorest group of people. The members of the Capitol mask the class system in the forms of television and entertainment.

On a personal note, I consider Hunger Games as one the best-written young adult novels. In the movie, you will notice that loyalty is tested, and trust is measured to its heights. You will also admire because it shows culture materialism where one can notice that in order to survive an adversity, one must know how to play the game just like what Katniss did when she was in the arena trying to survive in the game. We, too, experience different challenges in life that will test our courage and willingness to change. Like Katniss, she did not let her economic status and her gender paralyze her completely and proved to everyone that she could make a change if the will is bigger than her fear. She believed she could, so she did.

Katniss' touchingly vulnerable presence in the movie is just so convincing to me. She just embodies an ideal feminism of strength and courage, and that makes her a real tough nut to crack!

The movie also tells a story of oppression or manipulation of a less privileged social class by the social elite in a fight for survival. The film too emphasizes the power of love, sacrifice, and will power to overcome such adversity.

To top it all, the movie Hunger Games packs plenty of thematic depth and has all the technical ingredients of a great film.

Maureen's Murdock's Heroine's Journey

The movie shows the young female heroine, Katniss, who is not motivated by glory but by love and affection of the people around her. Let us see how Murdock's theory comes into play.

Separation

1. **The Ordinary World:** Katniss comes from District 12 which is a coal mining region of the nation known as Panem. When her father died in an explosion in the coal-mine, she becomes the primary breadwinner of the family. This is where Separation of Murdock comes in the picture and that is the separation of Katniss from her feminine side. To keep her family alive, she hunts in the wood and trades in the hob. She spends most of her time only with her mother, sister, and her close friend, Gale.
2. **The Call to Adventure:** The annual reaping day is just an ordinary day for Katniss until her sister, Prim, is selected to compete in the bloodbath tournament. Knowing this, Katniss has to make a tough decision whether to stay in the comfort zone where she finds peace and happiness with the people around her or to volunteer to take place Prim's place as tribute. Without a second thought, she takes Prim's place and willingly takes the challenge to fight in the Hunger Games. That kind of self-sacrifice is so rare.
3. **Refusal of the Call:** Before the reaping starts, she and Gale plan to run away from District 12. In fact, Gale tells her that he could bring Katniss and her family into the woods to get rid of the annual reaping day. However, it never happens.
4. **Supernatural Aid:** Katniss as seen in the movie does not receive any supernatural aid or help but is aided by her mentors, Haymitch and Effie and her stylist and designer, Cinna. These people are the ones who teach Katniss how to act in front of the camera and train her with the necessary skills she would need to ace in the interview in the Capitol.

5. **Crossing the Threshold:** Along with Peeta, Katniss from her old life in District 12 readies herself and travels to the Capitol for the tournament. The Capitol lavishes her with sumptuous food and luxurious clothes and accommodation.
6. **Belly of the Whale:** This is when Katniss enters the arena rising up from below ground where she there is no going back. She sees other tributes killing themselves and becomes an eye opening experience for her that she is a new but terrifying world.

Initiation

1. **The Road of Trials:** This happens when Katniss has to defend herself from the powerful attacks and dangerous encounters with her fellow tributes. In the process, she does not only learn how to fight and use her arrows and bow skillfully but also learns who to trust, who to stay away from, and how to get help she needs from her sponsors.
2. **Apotheosis:** When Katniss learns that her sister, Prim, died, she immediately finds her way home. She is in great pain and dies emotionally. After Prim's death, Katniss as illustrated by Tenpenny experiences an urgent yearning to reconnect with the feminine since she is back home.
3. **The Ultimate Boon:** To her anger, she plans to avenge her sister and those innocent people who lost their lives by killing President Coin and overthrowing the Capitol.

Return

1. **Refusal of the Return:** She struggles so much that she thinks she could not go back to the kind of life she used to have. The sight of revolution, war, and devastation is all she knows. Her perception of the world changes and cannot assimilate into the real world after she successfully kills President Coin and President Snow.
2. **The Magic Flight:** In the first movie, Katniss survives the first Hunger Games and returns home with pride and honor. Katniss though nearly dying at the end in the Catching Fire episode destroys the arena using electricity and her arrow. She is able to survive the battle only by using her spectacular archery skills even if she knows she had lost a lot along the way.
3. **Rescue from Without:** Katniss is deeply traumatized by her experience, so she needs help from her friends, Peeta and Haymitch to ease the suffering inside in order for her to figure out how to live again.
4. **The Crossing of the return Threshold:** Katniss finally returns home victorious despite the loss of Prim and her neighbors in District 12 as well as the innocent people in other districts.
5. **Master of Two Worlds:** Being able to adjust to the real hard is hard for Katniss to do since she is deeply traumatized by her experience. Before entering into the arena, she was able to live and survive in the ordinary world by hunting into the woods and trading what she got in the hob. So as to say with her experience into the battlefield where she was able to survive against all odds. I can say she gains so much knowledge from her quest which she can apply in the real world.
6. **Freedom to Live:** Katniss has finally overcome the trauma and is happily married to Peeta and is a proud parent of the two children. Katniss has maintained her being strong, willed, and self-sufficient. She still is equipped with the masculine and feminine characteristics in her. She does not lose her fire. She is still *the girl on fire!*